

Database of anthropogenic vegetation of Urals and adjacent territories

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Abstract

The Database of anthropogenic vegetation of Urals and adjacent territories (GIVD ID 00-RU-008) includes 4,327 vegetation plots of anthropogenic vegetation from 3 regions of the Russian Federation (the Republic of Bashkortostan, Orenburg, Chelyabinsk regions) and 1 region of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Aktobe region). All relevés were made between 1984 and 2021 AD. 1865 vegetation plots are from different literature sources (28 sources), 2462 are unpublished relevés from the authors. 94% of the relevés are geo-referenced. The ecological conditions were assessed by the use of average Landolt indicator values. The taxonomy of vascular species is given according to Cherepanov (1995). The vegetation plots in the database belong to nine vegetation classes. 7 anthropogenic (*Sisymbrietea*, *Digitario sanguinalis-Eragrostietea minoris*, *Polygono-Poetea annuae*, *Artemisietea vulgaris*, *Epilobietea angustifolii*, *Bidentetea*, *Robinietea*) and 2 semi-natural phytosociological classes: *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* (anthropogenically transformed meadows, lawns, etc. of the union *Cynosurion cristati* Tx. 1947.) and *Festuco-Brometea* (anthropogenically transformed steppe communities found within human settlements). Vegetation plots include also invasive species (*Acer negundo*, *Ambrosia trifida*, *Echinocystis lobata*, *Impatiens glandulifera*, *Solidago canadensis*, *Solidago gigantea*, *Heracleum sosnowskyi*, *Hordeum jubatum*, *Xanthium albinum* etc.).

Keywords

anthropogenic vegetation, Kazakhstan, Russia, TURBOVEG, Urals, vegetation classification, vegetation plot

GIVD Fact Sheet

GIVD Database ID: 00-RU-008		Last update: 2022-03-10	
Database of anthropogenic vegetation of Urals and adjacent territories Web address:			
Database manager(s): Yaroslav Golovanov (jaro1986@mail.ru); Larisa Abramova (abramova.lm@mail.ru)			
Owner: Yaroslav Golovanov, Senior researcher, South Ural Botanical garden-institute, Laboratory of wild-growing flora and introduction of herbaceous plants			
Scope: The database contains data on anthropogenic vegetation of the Urals (Republic of Bashkortostan, Orenburg, Chelyabinsk Regions) and adjacent territories.			
Abstract: Database of anthropogenic vegetation of Urals and adjacent territories. The database contains 4327 vegetation plots. The anthropogenic communities include synanthropic herb and woody species in semi-natural communities of settlements and their environments.			
Availability: according to a specific agreement	Online upload: no	Online search: no	
Database format(s): TURBOVEG	Export format(s): TURBOVEG		
Plot type(s): normal plots	Plot-size range (m ²): 1 to 400		
Non-overlapping plots: 4327	Estimate of existing plots: 4327	Completeness: 100%	Status: completed and continuing
Total no. of plot observations: 0	Number of sources (biblioreferences, data collectors): 28	Valid taxa: 0	
Countries (%): RU: 99,9; KZ: 0,1			
Formations: Forest: 2% = Terrestrial: 2% // Non Forest: 98% = Semi-aquatic: 4% (Fresh water: 4%); Terrestrial: 94% (Non arctic-alpin: 94% [Semi-natural: 2%; Anthropogenic: 93%])			
Guilds: all vascular plants: 100%			
Environmental data (%): altitude: 0; slope aspect: 0.5; slope inclination: 0.5; microrelief: 0; surface cover other than plants (open soil, litter, bare rock etc.): 0; other soil attributes: 0; soil pH: 0; land use categories: 0; soil depth: 0; other attributes: The ecological conditions were assessed with use of average values of E. Landolt (1977) scale. Average values are calculated on the following scales: humidification (M), acidity (R), soil richness with mineral nutrition elements (N), humus (H) content, mechanical composition and soil structure (D), illumination (L) etc.			
Performance measure(s): presence/absence only: 0%; cover: 100%; number of individuals: 0%; measurements like diameter or height of trees: 0%; biomass: 0%; other: 0%			
Geographic localisation: GPS coordinates (precision 25 m or less): 18.4%; point coordinates less precise than GPS, up to 1 km: 41.7%; small grid (not coarser than 10 km): 39.4%; political units or only on a coarser scale (above 10 km): 0.5%			
Sampling periods: 1980-1989: 17%; 1990-1999: 6%; 2000-2009: 26%; 2010-2019: 48%; unknown: 3%			
<i>Information as of 2022-03-10; further details and future updates available from http://www.givd.info/ID/00-RU-008</i>			

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